

ELECTRICAL AND THERMAL PROPERTIES OF NANOCOMPOSITES FILLED WITH HYBRIDS OF GRAPHENE OXIDE AND SILVER NANOWIRE

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1. Introduction

One-dimensional nanostructured particles such as nanowire, nanotubes, nanorods, or nanofibers are expected to play an important role in fabricating nanoscale devices and nanocomposites[1]. Agglomeration takes place frequently when nano particles are used to fabricate composites and generates problems that affect their performance. Surface modification is the most important step when different types of materials were blended into composites especially for nano-composites[2]. The simplest method to modify the surface of nano particles is the addition of surface modifying agent such as silane coupling agent.

Silver nanowires (AgNWs) with well-defined dimensions represent a particular class of interesting nanostructures to synthesize and study because bulk silver exhibits the highest electrical and thermal conductivity among all metals. Silver is also an important material that has been used in a rich variety of commercial applications, and the performance of silver in these applications could be potentially enhanced by processing silver into 1D nanostructures with controllable dimensions and aspect ratios. For example, the loading of silver in polymeric composites could be greatly reduced if nanoparticles were replaced by nanowires having higher aspect ratios. But, in spite of the advantages, because of the high density AgNW was subsides to the bottom of the base resin. To overcome this problem, graphene oxide (GO) was used as precipitation agent.

GO also has attracted much interest recently as a material with extraordinary electronic properties.

Graphene oxide itself is an insulator, almost a semiconductor, with differential conductivity [3].

Overcome settling and also to reduce the anisotropy, to sintering effect was expected. We used the characteristics of the GO to absorb a lot of the microwave, GO/AgNW was expected effects of the sintering. Scheme 1 shows the schematic illustration of the experimental procedure that was generates microwave irradiation handled GO/AgNW.

In this paper, we handled the microwave GO/AgNW hybrid thermal conductivity and electrical resistivity of the impact was studied.

2. Experimental

2.1 Chemicals and Materials.

Anhydrous ethylene glycol (EG, 99.8%), platinum chloride (PtCl₂, 99.99+%), silver nitrate (AgNO₃, 99+%), poly(vinyl pyrrolidone) (PVP, MW : 55 000), acetone, N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF : HPLC grade), aluminum acetylacetonate (AA) and flake of synthetic graphite (> 20μm) were purchased from Aldrich. Hydroxyl terminated poly (dimethylsiloxane) (PDMS) was purchased from Dow Corning. 2-(3,4-Epoxy cyclohexyl)ethyl-trimethoxysilane (ECTS) was purchased from Fluka. Celloxide 2021P was purchased from Daicel Chemical. Graphene oxide (GO) was prepared by modified Hummer's Method[4,5]. All chemicals were used without further purification.

2.2 Preparation of AgNWs

AgNWs were synthesized by reducing AgNO₃ with EG in the presence of Pt seeds and PVP. In a typical process, PtCl₂ solution in EG was added to EG heated upto 160 °C in a round-bottom flask

(equipped with a condenser, thermo controller, and magnetic stirring bar). After few minute, AgNO_3 in EG and PVP solution in EG were added drop wise (simultaneously) to the hot solution over a period. The reaction of the mixture was continued with heating at $160\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ until all AgNO_3 had been completely reduced. Vigorous stirring was maintained throughout the entire process. The simultaneous and dropwise addition of AgNO_3 and PVP solutions was critical to the formation of silver products with wire-like morphologies. Only the aforementioned procedure could lead to the formation of AgNWs with relatively high aspect ratios and uniform diameters, and at relatively high yields.

2.3 Preparation of Nanocomposite

Epoxy resin/silicone hybrids were synthesized through the cationic polymerization of a cycloaliphatic epoxy resin, hydroxyl-terminated PDMS and ECTS. Scheme 2 shows reaction of the epoxy resin/silicone hybrids. GO was exfoliated using a common household microwave oven. GO in the beaker under the nitrogen atmosphere was exposed to microwave irradiation at 180s. AgNW and exfoliated GO were dispersed in DMF solution. And mixture was sonicated at 200W for 4hours. Mixture was exposed to microwave irradiation at 30s 4 times again. The epoxy resin was mixing together with the GO/AgNWs solution and solvent was removed by evaporation at $98\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Solvent was further removed in vacuum oven at $30\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Composite pastes were cured at $150\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 6 hours and $200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ 1hour. The composites were irradiated with the microwave additionally 5 times for 2 seconds.

2.4 Characteristics

Morphology was examined using a scanning electron microscope (SEM, JSM-6400). In preparing the samples of AgNWs, they were purified by centrifugation. In this case, the reaction mixture was diluted with acetone (5x by volume) and centrifuged at 2000 rpm for 20min. The supernatant containing silver particles could be easily removed using a pipet. This centrifugation procedure were repeated several times until the supernatant became colorless (silver nanoparticles had a yellow tint due to the surface plasmon resonance). Product was dried one day in

vacuum oven. The products were spotted on carbon films. Transmission electron microscope (TEM, H-7650) was also employed observe AgNWs. The TEM samples were prepared by placing small droplets of the diluted (by $\sim 100\times$ with water) product solutions on copper grids. All the samples for TEM and SEM were allowed to dry at room temperature in a desiccator connected to vacuum pump. The surface electrical resistivity of the nanocomposite was measured using a surface electrical resistivity meter (JEOL, ST-3). Thermal conductivity was also measured using a thermal conductivity meter (Nanoflash, LFA447).

3. Results

The formation of anisotropic silver nanostructures involves at least two steps. In the first step, Pt nanoparticles with diameters on the order of 5 nm were formed by reducing PtCl_2 with ethylene glycol. In the second step, AgNO_3 and PVP were added dropwise to the reaction system, allowing the nucleation and growth of silver. As the reaction continued, the small silver particles were no longer stable in solution, and they started to dissolve and contribute to the growth of larger ones. With the assistance of PVP, some of the large nanoparticles were able to grow into rod-shaped structures with lateral dimensions in the range of 150-200 nm.

Scheme 1. Schematic illustration of the experimental procedure that was generates microwave irradiation handled GO/AgNW.

Scheme 2. Process to prepare the matrix resin of nanocomposites based on the hybrid resin.

Figure 1 shows the TEM image and SEM image of AgNWs after purification. Clearly confirm the removal of silver nanoparticles from this sample. The image also shows the straightness along the

Figure 1. (a) TEM and (b) SEM images of AgNWs.

Figure 2. Pictures of GO/AgNW dispersions in DMF : (a) GO/AgNW without microwave irradiation; (b) GO/AgNW after microwave irradiation.

Figure 3. TEM images of various GO/AgNW mixtures : (a) microwave irradiated mixture before centrifuge; (b) microwave irradiated mixture after centrifuge.

longitudinal axis, the level of perfection, and the copious in quantity that we could routinely achieve using this synthetic approach.

Figure 2 shows the microwave irradiated GO/AgNWs solution in DMF. The GO/AgNWs without microwave irradiation sample is stable. But after microwave irradiated GO/AgNWs solution is settle down indicate that the GO/AgNWs has a sintered by microwave irradiation.

Another evidence of sintering of GO/AgNWs has a TEM image. Figure 3 shows the TEM image of various GO/AgNWs mixture. Microwave irradiated mixture before centrifuged sample has many other Ag nanoparticles. But, after centrifuged sample do not appear other Ag particles and wires. It is indicated that GO and AgNWs has a well sintered. It was found that GO has a role of prevent settling agent and decrease the anisotropic properties of Ag NWs.

Figure 4 shows the surface electrical resistivity of the GO/AgNWs composites as a function of AgNWs content and microwave irradiation. GO content was fixed at 1wt%. The AgNWs content increase 8 to 10 wt%, surface electrical resistivity was started to decrease caused by the percolation threshold was occurred. But microwave irradiation treated composites has a lower AgNW content, at 6 to 8 wt%, surface electrical resistivity was start to decrease. By microwave irradiation, percolation threshold was decrease due to sintering effect of GO/AgNWs. That means microwave irradiation has a good method for the decrease surface electrical resistivity.

Figure 4. Surface electrical resistivity of the GO/Ag NWs composite as a function of AgNWs content and microwave irradiation (MI).

Table 1. Thermal conductivity of various compositions.

Sample code	Density (g/cm ³)	Diffusivity (mm ² /s)	Cp (J/gK)	K-value (W/mK)
Resin	0.920	0.154	2.900	0.411
GO-T	1.065	0.018	5.138	0.098
GO-M	1.228	0.606	0.836	0.608
Ag-T	2.509	0.783	0.744	1.462
Ag-M	2.594	0.761	0.761	1.502
GOAg-2T	0.868	0.395	1.325	0.454
GOAg-4T	1.487	0.420	1.005	0.627
GOAg-2M	1.421	0.457	1.145	0.744
GOAg-4M	2.226	0.717	0.885	1.412

Table 1 shows the vertical thermal conductivity of base resin, GO, Ag, GO/AgNWs. T means only thermal cured sample. AgNWs was fixed 10 vol %. M means microwave irradiation treated after thermal cure. For example, GOAg-2M, GO 2wt% and Ag 10 vol % was mixed with resin and microwave irradiation treated after thermal cure. Only thermal cured Ag has low K-value (1.462 W/mK) compare with microwave irradiation treated sample (1.502 W/mK). GOAg-2 and GOAg-4 sample has also same trend. It was found that the microwave irradiation has decrease the percolation threshold because of sintering effect of GO/AgNWs.

Conclusion

We prepared AgNWs by polyol method. AgNWs having uniform diameters in the range of 150 – 200 nm, and with controllable lengths up to 10 μm. And introduced microwave irradiation treated method in GO/AgNWs solution, and thermal cured sample, respectively. GO/AgNWs sintering was confirmed in TEM image and picture. By microwave irradiation, surface electrical resistivity decrease and thermal conductivity increase was confirmed. It was indicated that percolation threshold was occurred due to sintering effect of GO/AgNWs.

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